

ISic0951

I.Sicily inscription 0951

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of Vigna Cassia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6112

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Κλώδιος Ἦω
2. μανὸς ἔζη
3. σεν ἔτη · ι·θ ·
4. ἡμέρας · δ ·
5. ἀμέπτως τὸ(ν)
6. βίον ψυχὴ χαί
7. ρει · α[ι]·ώνιος

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492581

EDCS 39102108

PHI 140432

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0134 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.37

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